

Project Management Plan

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0. Executive Summary

This Project Management Plan presents information for the EERIE consortium members to understand the processes, procedures, roles and obligations of each partner. The described processes and procedures shall ensure an effective and clearly defined methodology for ensuring that EERIE is delivered as efficiently as possible. This document complements existing project documentation including the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement and should be used in conjunction with these two documents.

History of Changes

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
EERIE Project Office (EPO)	EERIE Coordinator & EERIE SSC	EERIE SSC

Issue	Date	Description	Author
1.0	24/03/2023	First final draft with revisions by SSC	EPO

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1. Introduction to the project

1.1. Scope

The ocean is known to affect our planet's climate. In this regard, mesoscale eddies, which constitute essentially the weather on the ocean, could be far more important than previously believed, especially when it comes to changes in a warming world. The project EERIE (European Eddy Rich Earth System Models) could significantly improve today's Earth system models and therefore projections of the climate's future development.

1.2. General information

- Full title: European Eddy Rich Earth System Models
- Project acronym: EERIE
- Duration: 4 years (start date: 1 January 2023)
- Budget: EUR 10.8 M (EUR 7.8 M EU, EUR 3M UK + CH)
- Call: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02
- Grant number: 101081383
- Participants: 12 Beneficiaries, 5 Associated Partners
- Participating countries: 9
- Website: <https://eerie-project.eu/>

1.3. Project structure

Figure 1: PERT Chart of the EERIE Project.

EERIE's WPs are structured into twelve work packages: WPs 1-4 are cutting across the project and underpin the other WPs. WP1 is the project management and coordination work package and will deliver the project management and scientific coordination, both within the project and with the international community. The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities across the project are contained in WP2, in addition to synthesising outcomes from the other WPs, and producing storylines as well as policy advice for communication to stakeholders and the public. WP3 will manage and publish the model data and ensure that it will be usable and discoverable by the community and by the assessment work packages (WP5-8). WP4 will perform the eddy-rich reference simulations, deliver the data to WP3 and make it available to WP5-8, and provide a benchmark of model performance. Simulations in WP4 will be done in two phases, the second phase starting in the second half of the project to benefit from the WP9-12 developments, and the scientific insights gained in WP5-8.

The PERT chart in Figure 1 indicates some of the interactions, dependencies and delivery of work packages components during the project.

2. Who is who? (people and teams)

2.1. Partners

Partners with EU-Funding (beneficiaries)

- 1) ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG (AWI), Germany
- 2) BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER-CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION (BSC CNS), Spain
- 3) UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN (UCT), South Africa
- 4) EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS (ECMWF), United Kingdom (international organization)
- 5) CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS (CNRS), France
- 6) PREDICTIA INTELLIGENT DATA SOLUTIONS SL (PREDICTIA), Spain
- 7) UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN (UCLouvain), Belgium
- 8) MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV (MPG | MPI-M), Germany
- 9) DEUTSCHES KLIMARECHENZENTRUM GMBH (DKRZ), Germany
- 10) UNIVERSITE DE YAOUNDE I (UYao), Cameroon
- 11) UNIVERSITAET BREMEN (UBREMEN), Germany
- 12) MINISTERIE VAN INFRASTRUCTUUR EN WATERSTAAT (PBL), Netherlands

Partners without EU-Funding (associated partners)

- 13) MET OFFICE (MET OFFICE), United Kingdom
- 14) THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD (UOXF), United Kingdom
- 15) UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (UKRI), United Kingdom
- 16) THE UNIVERSITY OF READING (UREAD), United Kingdom
- 17) EIDGENÖSSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH (ETH Zürich), Switzerland

Changes in the teams of the project partners

When a new person joins the project team of an EERIE partner, it is mandatory to inform the EERIE Project Office (EPO; eerie-project@awi.de). The EPO needs the following data: Name, gender, email address, name on MatterMost, dates of employment on EERIE and WPs the person is involved in. The EPO provides login details and includes the new team member in the appropriate mailing lists and MatterMost. The new team members should familiarise themselves with the information and documents available on the project's website <https://eerie-project.eu/> as well as on the dedicated EERIE Google Drive and in the relevant MatterMost channels.

If a team member leaves EERIE, it is also mandatory to inform the EPO (eerie-project@awi.de) to ensure removal from mailing and contact lists and the EERIE database.

Each partner's main contact, as listed in the project's Grant Agreement (the contract between the European Commission and the project partners), is responsible for promptly informing the EPO (eerie-project@awi.de) about any changes in the partners' project teams, especially regarding the representatives of the institution and members of EERIE consortium bodies.

The Consortium Agreement (the contract between the partners) contains information related with the responsibilities, rights and obligations of the project's partners, specifically in the following sections:

- 3.3 Survival of rights and obligations
- 4 Responsibilities of Parties
- 7.1.6 Financial Consequences of the termination of the participation of a Beneficiary
- 9.7 Access Rights for Parties entering or leaving the consortium
- 9.8 Specific Provisions for Access Rights to Software

The EERIE partners commit to embracing diversity, equity and inclusion as a prerequisite for excellence. By doing so the scientific performance as well as its human

interactions within and outside the project will be enhanced. We expect every project participant to understand and support this ambition which is partially represented by each partner's gender equality plan.

2.2. EERIE Consortium Bodies

2.2.1. EERIE Coordination Team & Project Office

The EERIE Coordinator and the EERIE Project Office (EPO) are based at the Alfred Wegener Institute in Bremerhaven and are composed of:

- Thomas Jung as the EERIE Coordinator (thomas.jung@awi.de), who is responsible for the overall scientific coordination and heads the EERIE Project Office.
- The EERIE Project Office (EPO): Nora Lawo and Jana Görner (eerie-project@awi.de) who are jointly responsible for operations, project management, and grant management (administration and finances).

The EERIE Coordination Team consists of the EERIE Coordinator and the Co-Coordination of EERIE:

- Malcolm Roberts (malcolm.roberts@metoffice.gov.uk) and
- Pier Luigi Vidale (p.l.vidale@reading.ac.uk).

The EERIE Co-Coordination also oversee and coordinate the UK part of the EERIE Consortium.

The EERIE Coordination Team together with the EPO is responsible for the overall project implementation and for representing the project at the international level. All matters related to dissemination, exploitation and communication management are addressed jointly with the WP2 Lead.

2.2.2. Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)

The EERIE Coordination Team is supported in the scientific coordination of the project by the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC):

The SSC is the supervisory body for the execution of EERIE. It is accountable to the EERIE Governing Board (GB) and reports to the GB usually once a year (more often if deemed necessary). The SSC ensures effective execution of actions through regular review of the coordination activities and implementation of the scientific project deliverables. It is composed of the Work Package Leads (WP Leads) and the WP Co-Leads (the WP Lead is mentioned first):

WP1: Project management and coordination

- Thomas Jung (thomas.jung@awi.de) as chair of the SSC
- Malcolm Roberts (malcolm.roberts@metoffice.gov.uk)

WP2: Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

- Markel García Díez (garciam@predictia.es)
- Gert Versteeg (gerrit.versteeg@bsc.es)

WP3: Data management

- Jon Seddon (jon.seddon@metoffice.gov.uk)
- Fabian Wachsmann (wachsmann@dkrz.de)

WP4: Frontier simulations and standard evaluation

- Malcolm Roberts (malcolm.roberts@metoffice.gov.uk)
- Thomas Jung (thomas.jung@awi.de)

WP5: Evaluation of ocean mesoscale processes and their interactions with the atmosphere and sea-ice

- Nicolas Gruber (nicolas.gruber@env.ethz.ch)
- Dian Putrasahan (dian.putrasahan@mpimet.mpg.de)

WP6: Impact of the ocean mesoscale on the state and change of the ocean

- Jin-Song von Storch (jin-song.von.storch@mpimet.mpg.de)
- Anne Marie Treguier (anne-marie.treguier@univ-brest.fr)

WP7: Impact of the ocean mesoscale on climate variability and teleconnections

- Christopher Roberts (chris.roberts@ecmwf.int)
- Hannah Christensen (h.m.christensen@atm.ox.ac.uk)

WP8: Role of the ocean mesoscale on regional expression of climate change

- Pablo Ortega (portega@bsc.es)
- Nicolas Gruber (nicolas.gruber@env.ethz.ch)

WP9: Efficient protocols for usable eddy-rich Earth System Modelling

- Pier Luigi Vidale (p.l.vidale@reading.ac.uk)
- Christopher Roberts (chris.roberts@ecmwf.int)

WP10: Model developments for realistic and efficient ER-ESMs

- Thomas Jung (thomas.jung@awi.de)
- Mario Acosta (mario.acosta@bsc.es)

WP11: Development of efficient and portable workflows and diagnostics for ER-ESMs

- Pierre-Antoine Bretonnière (pierre-antoine.bretonniere@bsc.es)
- Nikolay Koldunov (nikolay.koldunov@awi.de)

WP12: Enhancing models and model analysis with Machine Learning

- Hannah Christensen (h.m.christensen@atm.ox.ac.uk)
- Veronika Eyring (veronika.eyring@uni-bremen.de)

The WP Leads and WP Co-Leads oversee and implement work package activities and are directly responsible for fulfilling the work package objectives and managing work package matters, deliverables, milestones and work package progress reports. The WP Leads and WP Co-Leads report regularly on the progress within their work package to the SSC and are the first point of contact for the work package teams.

2.2.3. Governing Board (GB)

The Governing Board (GB) is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. It consists of one representative of each consortium member – including the *associated partners* who may not decide on EU internal matters, e.g. the EU contribution and parts of the Description of Action (DoA) they are not involved in:

- AWI:
Thomas Jung (thomas.jung@awi.de) as chair of the GB
- BSC CNS:
Pablo Ortega (portega@bsc.es)
- UCT:
Ross Blamey (ross.blamey@gmail.com)
- ECMWF:
Christopher Roberts (chris.roberts@ecmwf.int)
- CNRS:
Anne Marie Treguier (anne-marie.treguier@univ-brest.fr)
- PREDICTIA:
Markel García Díez (garciam@predictia.es)
- UCLouvain:
Hugues Goosse (hugues.goosse@uclouvain.be)
- MPG | MPI-M:
Jin-Song von Storch (jin-song.von.storch@mpimet.mpg.de)
- DKRZ:
Hannes Thiemann (thiemann@dkrz.de)
- UYao:
Wilfried Pokam (wpokam@yahoo.fr)

- UBREMEN:
Veronika Eyring (veronika.eyring@uni-bremen.de)
- PBL:
Detlef van Vuuren (detlef.vanvuuren@pbl.nl)
- *MetOffice*:
Malcolm Roberts (malcolm.roberts@metoffice.gov.uk)
- *UOXF*:
Hanna Christensen (h.m.christensen@atm.ox.ac.uk)
- *UKRI*:
Ag Stephens (ag.stephens@stfc.ac.uk)
- *UREAD*:
Pier Luigi Vidale (p.l.vidale@reading.ac.uk)
- *ETH Zürich*:
Nicolas Gruber (nicolas.gruber@env.ethz.ch)

These representatives have been authorised to decide and negotiate all EERIE related matters on behalf of their institutions.

2.2.4. External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)

The EERIE Consortium Bodies are supported by an External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) of distinguished scientists to ensure external advice on the project and links to other activities both outside and within Europe. The EEAB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the EERIE Governing Board (GB) to ensure the maximum impact (and legacy) of EERIE. All EERIE EEAB members have to sign an NDA so that information can be freely shared with them and they can attend all EERIE project meetings.

(Status 24.03.2023: 1 NDA is still missing.)

EEAB Member	Email	Profession and organisation (as of 03/2023)
Dr Ping Chang	ping@tamu.edu	Professor, Department of Oceanography and Dept. of Atmospheric Sciences, Texas A&M University (TAMU), director of iHESP
Dr Carol Anne Clayson	cclayson@whoi.edu	Senior Scientist Physical Oceanography, WHOI
Dr James Edson	jedson@whoi.edu	Senior Scientist, Applied Ocean Physics and Engineering, WHOI
Professor Pierre Gentine	pg2328@columbia.edu	Professor of Geophysics and Director of the Center for Learning the Earth with Artificial Intelligence and Physics (LEAP), Columbia University, USA
Dr Pierre-Yves Le Traon	pierre-yves.lettraon@mercator-ocean.fr	Scientific Director, Mercator-Ocean and Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service , France
Dr Nada Caud	nada.caud@lsce.ipsl.fr	Communications project manager, Climate and Environmental Science Laboratory LSCE (a Mixed Research Unit CEA, CNRS, UVSQ), France

3. Reporting to the European Commission / CINEA

3.1. Project timeline

Figure 2: Reporting timelines

Main events and indicative dates	
01 January 2023	Project Start
23-24 February 2023	Kick-off Meeting (remote)
06-08 November 2023	General Assembly 1 (in Bremerhaven)
April 2024	Periodic Report 1
June 2024	Project Review Meeting 1
Autumn 2024	General Assembly 2
September 2025	Periodic Report 2
Autumn 2025	General Assembly 3
November 2025	Project Review Meeting 2
Autumn 2026	General Assembly 4
31 December 2026	Project End, Project Review Meeting 3 and Final Report

A detailed Gantt chart of the project including the schedule of all tasks and deliverables as of March 2023 can also be found in the EERIE Project’s Google Drive. The chart will be updated with any changes as they happen:

WP/Task	Title	Lead	Start	Finish	Reporting Period 1												Reporting Period 2												Reporting Period 3																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																				
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3.2. Deliverables

The Deliverable Leaders are responsible for the implementation of the individual deliverables as set out in the work plan. This includes establishing and managing interactions (in-person and virtual) between individual partners involved in the deliverables; establishing and maintaining links to other deliverables as described in the work plan (List of Deliverables: Grant Agreement, page 93), and as the deliverables evolve; and reporting of deliverable progress along with identified risks or concerns to WP Leads and WP Co-Leads.

The quality of a deliverable will be measured and verified against the project Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A (Description of Action). The Deliverable Leader (i.e., the beneficiary indicated in the Description of Action) is responsible for coordinating and following up on the work required for the Deliverable and for delivering the related Deliverable Report which describes the deliverable. The WP Leads and WP Co-Leads are responsible for overseeing the work required for the Deliverable and for interacting with the Deliverable Leaders who draft the Deliverable Report. The WP Leads and Co-Leads are expected to inform the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) well in advance, should there be any concerns regarding upcoming deliverables. The Deliverable Report will be drafted according to a template provided by the EERIE Project Office (EPO) together with the WP2 Lead, which can be adapted depending on the deliverable itself.

The deliverable report needs to include:

- Cover and second page with information related to the project and the deliverable (mandatory)
- Table of contents (mandatory)
- Executive summary or abstract (mandatory) including main message
- Introduction including structure of the report
- Core (e.g., methods, results, discussion, timeline)
- Collaborations with other deliverables / WPs
- External collaborations (e.g., stakeholders, other projects or programmes)
- Policy relevance / societal benefits
- Impact and exploitation (e.g., key performance indicators)
- References (e.g., acronyms, literature, annexes).

The EERIE Coordinator has authority and responsibility for quality management. He might approach members of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) for additional expert review of the deliverable to ensure quality. The EERIE Project Office (EPO) is responsible for finalising the deliverable and for submission to the European Commission (EC). The review process after submission to the EC includes the review of each deliverable by external experts who can recommend revisions or rejection of the report if the quality is not sufficient, the report does not outline the deliverable at hand properly or the work has not been implemented properly.

Four weeks prior to the deliverable deadline at the latest, the deliverable leaders will submit the draft deliverable report to the WP Leads and WP Co-Leads as well as the EERIE Coordinator and the EPO for review. If deliverable leaders wish for feedback from specific project partners or the SSC beforehand, they are free to publicise the deliverable via Google Drive before that four-week deadline.

The final deliverable report, approved by both the WP Leads and WP Co-Leads as well as the EERIE Coordination Team, needs to be submitted to the EPO two weeks prior to the submission deadline at the latest. The EPO will take care to submit the Deliverable to the EC through the EU Portal.

3.3. Milestones

The achievement of the project's milestones is demonstrated against the relative means of verification indicated in the Description of Action (List of Milestones: Grant Agreement, page 113). The lead beneficiary of each milestone is responsible for the verification of its achievement according to the schedule and will provide the EERIE Coordinator and Project Office (EPO) with a concise report for the records (1-3 pages, cover and abstract as for the deliverable report above) additionally to the means of verification included in the List of Milestones (Grant Agreement, page 113). When a milestone is achieved and verified, the lead beneficiary will inform the respective WP Leads and WP Co-Leads who are responsible for confirming and informing the EERIE Coordinator and the EPO. The EPO will then update the status of the achieved milestone in the EU Portal.

3.4. Project reports

No official interim reports are deemed necessary at this stage. In each meeting of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC), the WP Leaders are asked to report on their WPs and possible risks therein.

EERIE is divided into three reporting periods:

RP1: 1 January 2023 – 30 April 2024

RP2: 1 May 2024 – 30 September 2025

RP3: 1 October 2025 – 31 December 2026.

Within 60 calendar days from the end of each period the Project Consortium will submit a periodic report to the European Commission (EC). The periodic report is composed of a technical report and a financial report:

3.4.1. Technical report

The technical report is a detailed report of all activities and results of each of the WPs and of the project management. Technical reports are useful reference for recording the project's information and activities including explanations for possible deviations from the initial project plan. It is therefore very important that the project's main achievements and impact are clearly identifiable in the report.

Workflow:

Towards the end of each reporting period, the EERIE Project Office (EPO) will share with each WP Lead and WP Co-Lead a template (previously agreed with the EERIE Coordination Team and the Scientific Steering Committee, SSC) to report on the progress of their deliverable teams. This report is the contribution of each WP to the joint Technical Report. It is responsibility of the WP Leads and WP Co-Leads to collect and compile the information for each deliverable team according to the template and of all the partners to provide any additional information as requested for the portal (e.g., gender statistics, data related to publications and dissemination activities etc.). The WP Leads and WP Co-Leads will have about four weeks to provide the EPO and the EERIE Coordination Team with their reports. The WP reports will then be compiled by the EPO and reviewed by the EERIE Coordination Team and possibly SSC members might be assigned with this task as well, who will provide feedback. The final version will be compiled by the EERIE Coordination Team and submitted in the EU Portal together with the financial reports by the EPO.

The dissemination work is to be kept up to date constantly by every partner in joint Google Tables. The summary is added in the EU Portal by the EPO.

3.4.2. Financial report

The financial report is composed of all the financial reports from the project partners, which need to be submitted online through the EU portal. The EPO will collect and review the provided information. Each partner is in charge of their own finance management according to their organisational procedures and need to be able to provide information on their finance timely when requested. Detailed guidelines for financial reporting will be provided to partners in advance of the reporting period.

Workflow:

Towards the end of each reporting period, the EPO will provide all administrative contacts with a guideline document on the upcoming financial reporting. The guidelines consist of a detailed timetable stating all deadlines, written instructions on how to prepare the report, screenshots on what the different EU portal sites will look

like and what steps need to be performed. The guideline document further contains examples of needed information and the contact details of the EPO for further information and in case of queries.

The partners will have ca. three weeks to enter a first draft financial report into the EU portal. This draft financial report will be cross-checked by the EPO on its consistency, logic and understandability. In case of queries, the EPO will directly contact the partner(s) for further information. Once all issues in question are clarified, the partner will sign and submit their financial report to the Coordinator (role in the EU Portal), who will include the partner's financial report in the general reporting. The EPO will submit the financial report to the EC.

4. Project meetings

4.1. General Assemblies (GA)

The EERIE General Assemblies are held annually in person or online or as a combination (hybrid) with the aim to network and give the opportunity to all the project partners and collaborators to convene and update on the project progress as well as to discuss open issues. General Assemblies will be organised on working days only, not on weekends or public holidays for any of the countries participating in the project. As the General Assembly is the main governing body of the Consortium, attendance of all project partners is mandatory.

A typical programme includes update presentations of the EERIE Coordinator and EERIE Project Office (EPO) and all work packages (WP), presentations from guests/related projects programmes (e.g., nextGEMS, DestinE and OptimESM), contribution(s) from the EU Project Adviser and/or other relevant representatives, breakout sessions for the WP or Deliverable teams (as requested), activities targeted at early career scientists and social/networking activities. Activities targeted at early career scientists (e.g., hackathons or networking) might involve weekends.

General Assemblies are organised by the EERIE Coordination Team and the EPO with support from the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC). Information on the meetings, including logistical information and programme, and materials will be shared on the chosen internal communication channels and repository of documents (mostly MatterMost and Google Drive) as well as the project website (public information).

4.2. Work Package (WP) Meetings

Meetings with the WP (work package) teams are encouraged with frequency and modalities left to the WP Leads and WP Co-Leads to decide. WP Leads and WP

Co-Leads should inform the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) and the EERIE Coordinator and EERIE Project Office (EPO) on the WP meetings in writing (e.g. via the dedicated MatterMost event channel) or at the earliest opportunity (e.g. at the SSC meetings). This should also serve to allow participation of other WP Leads and WP Co-Leads to enhance interaction of the WPs.

Summaries of the WP meetings shall be shared with the whole WP team and the EERIE Coordinator and the EPO in the relative WP directory on the project's Google Drive. A template will be provided by the WP2 Lead in the WP2 folder on Google Drive.

4.3. Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) Meetings

Meetings of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) are organised and held by the EERIE Coordination Team and the EERIE Project Office (EPO) four times per year online and in person at the General Assemblies. SSC meetings are intended to update on the project progress, discuss issues, monitor and control the project implementation, keep track of project risks, impact (e.g., project presence at international conferences, publications, and other communication and dissemination activities), data provision, and any other relevant aspect. An agenda will be shared in advance of the meeting by the EERIE Coordinator or the EPO and a summary of the meeting will be shared with the SSC and stored on the project's Google Drive.

Standing agenda for SSC meetings includes (but is not limited to) the following items:

- 1) Updates from the both the EERIE Coordination Team and the EPO:
general updates/requests, admin/finances
- 2) Progress and possible issues in the work packages (WPs):
e.g., on work progress, deliverables/milestones, reports from events, upcoming events/meetings, new team members, finances
- 3) Clustering
- 4) Upcoming events:
project events, conferences of general interest
- 5) Risks:
Updates to risk register, e.g., risk status, new risks
- 6) Upcoming reports (to be discussed as needed)
- 7) Results tracking (to be discussed as needed, e.g., in conjunction with reports)
- 8) Miscellaneous

4.4. Governing Board (GB) Meetings

Meetings of the Governing Board (GB) are organised and held by the EERIE Coordination Team once per year at the General Assemblies. Further online meetings will be held, if needed.

The GB decides on matters regarding content, finances and intellectual property rights (as, e.g., planned changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement), regarding the Consortium (as, e.g., changes in the partners, a partial or complete suspension of EERIE), regarding breaches of a party's obligations under the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement and litigation. The GB is also responsible for appointing the members of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) and the External Expert Advisory Board Members (EEAB).

An agenda will be shared in advance of the meeting by the EERIE Coordinator or the EERIE Project Office (EPO) and a summary of the meeting will be shared with the GB and stored on the project's Google Drive. In general, all minutes are public within the Consortium, however, in some cases, sensitive issues might be kept confidential and are removed from the public minutes.

5. Impact and exploitation

Assessing the impact of activities carried out within EERIE is very important to gather a better understanding of climate projections and modelling of climate tipping points, as well as to provide further input to the next IPCC report and to strengthen Europe's climate modelling community. Section 2.1 of the Description of Action Part B details the expected project impact in contribution to the call topics as well as the additional impacts.

Measures to maximise the project's impact are outlined in Section 2.2 of the Description of Action Part B. The dissemination and communication strategies will rely on **two main pillars**: the **storylines** and the **Data Viewer**.

The **storylines** will follow two approaches, physical climate and impact, and they will help integrate domain and sectoral knowledge into development of plausible futures. This will improve the relevance of climate information by introducing local ways of relating to and coping with climate change. Storylines are a powerful tool for improving risk awareness, and will target specific sectors, as well as policymakers, helping them root climate governance into social life and strengthening the science-society- policy interface.

The **Data Viewer** will be developed by PREDICTIA, following their successful experience in developing the [Interactive Atlas](#) for the IPCC AR6. The Data Viewer will act as a showcase to navigate, consult and analyse the outputs produced by the project.

Due to the scientific nature of this project, a separate data management plan (DMP) will be executed, under WP3, to ensure that the data governance of the project is on track. To this end, EERIE will follow best-practice open science measures. We will ensure model data follows FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability,

and Reusability), and will make the results of EERIE as open and accessible as possible to all interested parties. The updated DMP will be provided in month six of the project (D3.1) and further updated throughout the project.

The project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategies are provided in Deliverables D2.1 – D2.7.

It is the responsibility of all partners to actively engage in dissemination and to report to WP2 Leads, what activities they engage in. Google Drive and Zenodo as online databases to track outreach and dissemination activities are in place and accessible for all partners to fill.

5.1. Publications and all dissemination work

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) will be used as repository for publications and data sets. The project's publications can be tracked with a log sheet available on the project's Google Drive.

Why do we need to track publications? The number of publications, the type of journal, and the number of citations (when tracking is possible) are all indicators of the scientific production of the project (and its uptake).

Open Access Policy: According to the Grant Agreement (Art. 17 and further specifications on art. 17 in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, pp. 211 sqq.) all publications and datasets outcoming from project activities need to be freely accessible.

Any dissemination of results **must include all funding acknowledgements (EU, UK, CH)**:

It needs to include the European flag and funding statement for acknowledgment (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

For articles, where no EU emblem can be displayed, please still include the funding statement as text in the acknowledgment section of your paper:

This publication is part of the EERIE project funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Please always add also the funding notes for CH and UK:

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract #22.00366.

This work was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (grant number 10040510).

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the **following disclaimer** (translated into local languages where appropriate):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

5.2. Dissemination and communication activities

Monitoring dissemination and communication activities is critical to maximize the impact of scientific findings to end-users. Meetings, conferences and workshops, press releases, webinars and videos are all fundamental platforms for the dissemination of project results. The impact of these activities can not only be measured in terms of how many events have been attended or organised by project scientists, but it is also worth considering the nature of the event (i.e., the type of event, size, targeted community, type of arrangement, etc.) to identify the target audiences and thus the impact of the activity.

Dissemination and communication activities carried out in the project can be tracked with a log sheet available on the EERIE Google Drive. Please refer also to chapter 5.1.

5.3. Project data

All project data (referring to documents, not the ESM data the project works with), under work or finalised, will be located or linked on the EERIE Google Drive. Here one folder per work packages is available. A welcoming document with important notes for new EERIE members is stored data secure on AWI NextCloud (read only). All users are asked to check the cross-cutting folders WP1 and WP2, as they contain relevant information for all (i.e., templates, logos, sheets to fill in dissemination work, ...). All EERIE team members have access to all EERIE Google Drive folders and can upload data or modify these.

The scientific data produced or collected within the project are managed according to the project's data management plan (DMP; D3.1) which includes the organisation, storage, preservation, and sharing of data collected and used in the project in compliance with FAIR principles.

5.4. Intellectual Property

As per the Description of Action (DoA, Part B of the Grant Agreement), the EERIE Coordinator is responsible for the management of intellectual property rights (IPR) for the project. Publications, licensing, patents, and other exploitation of the results will be tracked by each partner on Google Drive. On the management of the project's intellectual property, the EERIE Project Office (EPO) will be supported and advised by the EU Project Adviser and AWI's legal department.

6. Communication

6.1. Internal Communication

The preferred method for communication within the project [i.e., for general and important announcements, scientific discussions (with different topic-oriented channels)] is via MatterMost (<https://mattermost.com/>). One channel was set up for general announcements (upcoming dates and events) and one channel for each work package (WP1-12). Joint channels can be created individually on demand. All persons working in EERIE are asked to check their own scientific channels as well as the channels for WP1 (project management and coordination; PM) and WP2 (Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication; DEC).

For collaborative work Google Drive is used (<https://www.google.com/intl/en/drive/>). One folder per work packages is available and a welcoming document with important notes for new EERIE members. Again, all persons working in EERIE are asked to check their own scientific WP folders as well as the folders for WP1 (PM) and WP2 (DEC).

Several mailing lists have been set up by EPO for important announcements [e.g., Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) and Governing Board (GB) matters]. As a fall-back option, the whole scientific community of the project can be reached via eerie-science@listserv.dfn.de. For all other issues, separate contact lists are maintained by EPO. The main project communication works through the dedicated MatterMost channels.

Other means of communication used within the project includes videoconferencing (mostly via Webex).

6.2. External Communication

Communications with the European Commission, specifically with the Project Adviser Richard Travares are the responsibility of the EERIE Project Office (EPO) together with the EERIE Coordinator. The Project Adviser is the primary point of contact of the

project for any issue related with the project's implementation and administration including finances. All partners who wish to communicate with the CINEA / the European Union regarding EERIE need to approach the EPO.

EPO together with PREDICTIA are the first point of contact of EERIE with the public. The project website is also used as the primary source of information for the public. The website can be found at <https://eerie-project.eu/> and is maintained by PREDICTIA with input provided by all EERIE members. A detailed description of the project's communication channels including website and social media along with their strategy of use as a mean of dissemination of the project results and news is provided by PREDICTIA in the DEC plan (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication) by month six.

7. Project Administration and Finances

7.1. Grant Management

The EERIE Grant Agreement (the contract between the European Commission and the Consortium) was signed by both parties and entered into force on 4 October 2022.

A Consortium Agreement (the contract between the partners participating in the project) was set up by the Coordinator and discussed within the full consortium. It was finalised on 24 August 2022 and signed by all partners with the effective date of 1 January 2023. The Consortium Agreement is valid to all partners, irrespective of them receiving EC-Funding or not. All new partners will enter the Consortium Agreement by signing an Accession Form.

7.2. EU-Portal:

Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal

User's quick guide:

The management of the project is performed in the Funding and Tenders Portal under: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>

The portal holds processes for the Continuous Reporting of the project, the Periodic Reporting (if running) and further interactions with the EU like Amendments. It will be kept updated by the EERIE Project Office (EPO) unless specific input is required by the administrative partner contacts which will then be approached by EPO directly. During the Periodic Reporting, the Financial Report, data will be entered by all partners themselves, cross-checked by EPO and finally submitted to the EU by the Coordinator (as role in the EU Portal).

The main entrance to the system is the Grant Management Service site 'My project'.

Figure 4: Exemplary screenshot of the "Manage Project" page

The main continuous tasks in the EU Portal like submitting Deliverables, but also the general communication with the relevant EU contacts, will be done by the EPO.

The partners will receive extensive guidance on how to use the EU Portal sites, especially during Financial Reporting. A guide explaining the necessary steps will be handed to all partners in advance and during reporting support will be offered to all partners but especially to the inexperienced partners.

8. Risk management

EERIE project partners operate in an area of uncertainty that comes along with developing new and unique methodologies to deliver scientific findings. By doing so they take chances, which results in risk playing a significant part in the project. Through a methodical iterative process, the EERIE Project Office (EPO) and Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) identified and compiled the various risks in the List of Critical Risks. To ensure that monitoring is continuous throughout the life of the project, the List of Critical Risks will be updated by the EPO according to risk assessments at the SSC

meetings in case of necessity, including status of identified risks, new risks, and resolved risks.

Monitoring of risks is essential to ensure the project success and delivery of the results. Updates on risks and response strategies are to be delivered to the EC at the end of each reporting period.

9. Agile management

The EERIE Project Office (EPO) applies agile methodologies to the management of the project and the idea that changes are not challenges but rather opportunities to adapt and achieve success. In line with this mindset and the scientific approach to discovery, changes in the project (e.g., team composition, work plan) are welcome and implemented accordingly. Any changes are discussed with the interested beneficiaries and teams, the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) and the Project Adviser when appropriate. Any amendment request to the project's DoA (the project's workplan) needs to be submitted to the EPO which will ensure the Project Adviser is informed and included in the process.

Updates of this project management plan are the responsibility of the EPO (at reporting stages).